

FACTORS AFFECTING ACADEMIC STRESS AMONG MANAGEMENT UNDERGRADUATES DURING ONLINE LEARNING IN SRI LANKA

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Introduction

The online mode of education has begun with the advent of the Internet in 1990s. The main purpose of that acquisition was in transferable skills in communication and information technology (Volery and Lord, 2000). In the transformation from physical learning to online learning, the students had to face many more circumstances as making space to develop social interactions, teamwork, and personality management development, knowing about others, and taking part in extracurricular activities (Hayashi et al., 2020). Moreover, it affects badly university students' mental well-being in stressful situations among them (Agolla, J., & Ongori, H., 2009). Academic stress is a situation that is widespread in the different stages of the educational system, and it adversely affects students' personal, emotional, and physical well-being (García-Ros et al., 2018). According to university students, Academic Stress is a commonly experienced mental health issue, mostly due to worrying about having lost grades for some subjects and fear of failing exams. Academic Stress among students has been researched by previous researchers and identified some factors that caused stress as too many assignments, competition with peer students, failure in examinations, lack of pocket money, poor connections with

students or lecturers, family, or problems at home. Agolla & Ongori,H (2009). Mahees (2020) describes that excessive academic workload, economic hardships, problems in personal relationships, issues of family background, ragging, student politics, poor infrastructure facilities in hostels, and external social or cultural pressure on students are the major factors that affect stress among students when the universities were in physical mode. Researchers at the University of Colombo have found that some leading factors affecting stress among undergraduates are heavy academic workload, hardships in the family economy, relationship problems, and collective student behavior such as ragging, hostel life, and cultural pressure at the university (Mahees M.T, 2020). However, academic workload and personal relationships are found to be the most crucial factors compared to the other factors. According to Weerasinghe et al, 2012 study, the academic workload was found as the best predictor of an undergraduate's stress while a large amount of content to be learned and examinations were also significant predictors. Loneliness leads to emotional separation, pain, and impaired cognitive abilities, which can be reasoned with performance and health. There is a positive relationship between loneliness and academic stress among undergraduates during online learning mostly because online learning may cause separation of undergraduates from their peers at the university (Munir T.et al, 2015).

The review of the previous studies conducted based on the area of factors affecting academic stress among undergraduates during online learning is limited according to the Sri Lankan context. The study conducted by Madhusanka et al., (2021) is based on this area of factors affecting the level of stress among undergraduates in SL with special reference to COVID-19,

only considered an online learning experience and university workload as the main factors that resulted the undergraduates' level of stress during online learning in Sri Lanka. Thus, this study attempts to fill that gap by conducting the study based on,

“Factors affecting the academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning”.

Since, the present study models a new conceptual framework with three independent variables of the lack of online learning facilities, university workload, and loneliness factors affecting the undergraduates' academic stress during online learning as gained from reviewing previous studies as lack of online learning facilities was found as a significant factor that contributes academic stress. This finding was consistent with the findings of previous studies (Madhusanka et al., 2021; Adarkwah, M, 2021; Day et al, 2021). The academic workload is another significant factor that has a positive effect on academic Stress. This finding was consistent with the findings of previous studies (Agolla, J & Ongori, H 2009; Misra and McKean 2000; Madhusanka et al, 2021; Mahees M.T, 2020). Finally, loneliness was also found as a significant factor of academic stress. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies (Munir et al., 2015; Zhai. Y, Du. X, 2020; Leung L,2008). Thus, taking the undergraduates from the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura as the main research population, the study attempts to shed light on the factors affecting academic stress.

Based on that research problem, it was planned to address the following research questions

1. What are the factors affecting academic stress among management undergraduates of Sri Jayewardenepura University during online learning?
2. What is the relationship between identified factors and academic stress of management undergraduates of Sri Jayewardenepura University during online learning?

Based on those, the following research objectives were developed

1. To identify the factors which affect academic stress among management undergraduates of Sri Jayewardenepura University during online learning.
2. To identify the relationship between identified factors and academic stress of management undergraduates of Sri Jayewardenepura University during online learning.

Methodology

The study was undertaken as a quantitative approach to determining the relationship between the factors affecting (independent variables) academic stress (dependent variable) among around 130 undergraduates, which was taken from an a priori sample size calculator for Multiple Regression of Daniel Soper's statistical calculator from the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce of the University of Sri Jayewardenepura during online learning. According to the Webometrics world university ranking, University of Sri Jayewardenepura is the third best university in Sri Lanka considering several factors, including impact, openness, and excellence (Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), 2023). The Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce (FMSC) has been the

gateway to success for over 50,000 students (ITRC, 2022). In this study, the sample was selected to identify the factors affecting academic stress during online learning among undergraduates.

The conceptual model consists of three independent variables namely lack of online learning facilities (LOLF), university workload (UW), and loneliness (L), and one dependent variable of academic stress (AS).

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

In order to meet the research objectives, three research hypotheses were formulated as follows.

H1: There is a positive impact of the lack of online learning facilities on academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning.

H2: There is a positive impact of academic workload on academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning.

H3: There is a positive impact of loneliness on academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning.

This study is a cross-sectional study because the data was gathered are just one point in time. For identifying the representative sample, an individual undergraduate from FMSC at USJ was selected using convenience sampling for generating hypotheses that can be tested in greater depth. The sample size was calculated using a priori sample size calculator for Multiple Regression of Daniel Soper's statistical calculator. The data was gathered through an online questionnaire. It consisted of 12 questions gained from reviewing previous literature, which included multiple choice demographical data, and linear scale questions from the references. The collected data was analysed using the computer software known as SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) for descriptive statistics and SmartPLS for inferential statistics.

Results & Discussion

The reliability and validity of the constructs were evaluated prior to the model testing (Heale, L., & Twycross,A, 2015). The internal consistency reliability is measured through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. Among them, Cronbach's alpha is the most common instrument for determining internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha results were LOLF 0.707, UW 0.857, L 0.935, and AS 0.795. All the independent variables and dependent variables were greater than 0.7. Therefore, that ensured the validity of each variable was greater than 0.7. This research study showed convergent validity and discriminant validity to test the validity of the measurement model. Convergent validity is measured via the average variance extracted. It indicates the correlation within the constructs. Convergent validity is satisfied based on values gained from the average

variance extracted. They were greater than 0.5. The discriminant validity was measured through the Fornell- Lacker Criterion and Heterotrait – Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). According to the values gained through the SmartPLS, discriminant validity was also satisfied, there were no issues under the criteria.

Empirical results of the study suggest that all three variables as lack of online learning facilities, university workload, and loneliness factors positively influence the dependent variable of academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura as mentioned in below Table 1.

Table 1: Hypothesis Testing Results

	Original sample (0)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	P Values	Outcome
L=>AS	0.288	0.29	0.081	3.564	0	Supported
LOLF=>AS	0.327	0.333	0.096	3.393	0.001	Supported
UW=>AS	0.26	0.256	0.127	2.046	0.041	Supported

Conclusion

According to the findings, all three independent variables have a positive relationship with academic stress among management undergraduates during online learning. Therefore, it can be concluded that management undergraduates have academic stress during online learning. This research will contribute new knowledge to the existing field due to the conceptual model. The model comprised three independent variables;lack of online

learning facilities, academic workload, and loneliness affecting the dependent variable of undergraduates' academic stress. Therefore, it opens up a new area of study providing comprehensive knowledge on the undergraduates' grievances and differences among the undergraduates in terms of facilities and opportunities they have during online learning. Moreover, it is worthwhile to establish a proper system to identify stressed undergraduates as soon as possible in order to prevent unfavourable consequences of stress on them. This study will be useful source for undergraduates, lecturers, councillors, and university administrators to take action to minimize the effects of academic stress on undergraduates during online learning. One of the major limitations of the study was receiving accurate responses from the participants, as the questionnaire was administered using Google Forms; potentially, respondents provided their responses without fully concentrating. Further, the study's exclusive emphasis was only on undergraduates in the faculty of management studies and commerce at Sri Jayewardenepura University. However, this study sheds light on future research on virtual learning in the field of education.

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